

KIOS CoE Sandboxing Architecture for cyber-physical analysis

1.1 Introduction

A sandboxing environment leveraging digital twin and HIL technologies provides a cutting-edge platform for cyber-physical analysis (including cyber security investigations) in modern power systems. This environment creates a highly realistic, controlled, and non-invasive setting where researchers and engineers can simulate and study the behaviour of power systems under various cyber-attack scenarios. The digital twin aspect involves creating a virtual replica of the physical power system, including all its components and operational dynamics. This virtual model operates in parallel with the actual hardware, allowing for real-time monitoring, control, and analysis without risking the integrity of the live system.

Incorporating HIL enhances the fidelity of the simulations by integrating real hardware components into the virtual environment. This integration enables the sandbox to mimic the complex interactions between software and physical devices, providing a comprehensive view of potential vulnerabilities and the impact of cyber-attacks. Researchers can deploy and test various cyber-security strategies, identify weaknesses, and develop robust defence mechanisms within this controlled setting. By combining digital twin and HIL technologies, this sandboxing environment offers a powerful tool for advancing cyber-security in power systems, ensuring resilience and reliability in the face of evolving threats.

This section introduces the sandboxing environment initially designed and developed by the research team of KIOS CoE of the University of Cyprus to support the research activities and generation of realistic datasets for the ELECTRON¹ project, and then adapted to also support IT/OT cyber tests for the COCOON² project. It is designed to provide a holistic and non-invasive framework for emulating various cyber-attacks and investigating their impacts on modern electrical power and energy systems (EPES). This advanced sandboxing environment serves as a versatile platform for exploring a wide range of smart grid applications, such as wide area monitoring, control and protection, power system protection schemes, and active distribution grids and microgrids management among many possible others. The sandboxing environment facilitates several critical functions, including the **creation of datasets for cyber-security** for IT and OT infrastructures for EPES studies, for the training and testing of digital services in the form of cyber security applications, as well as for integration with specific external applications (e.g., intrusion detection and mitigation) and to evaluate their performance in a non-invasive setting. By enabling these capabilities, the sandbox ensures a comprehensive approach to cyber-security research and development within the power sector. In the following subsections, a detailed description of the overall sandboxing architecture of the KIOS CoE is provided. This includes an in-depth look at each layer of the architecture, such as the digital twin, power- and control-HIL, communication layer, cyber-attack layer, and integration with third-party applications.

1.2 KIOS CoE Sandboxing Architecture

The primary objective of the KIOS CoE sandboxing environment is to provide a flexible and non-invasive platform for conducting cyber-attacks on realistic power system operations. This allows

¹ <https://electron-project.eu/>

² <https://www.cyber-cocoon.eu/>

for comprehensive impact assessments and the evaluation of cyber-security solutions without jeopardizing the integrity of the power infrastructure.

1.2.1 Functional requirements

Within this context, the key functional requirements of the environment have been identified as follows:

- **Accurate and real-time emulation:** The sandboxing environment must accurately and in real-time emulate the dynamic operations of modern power systems. This emulation should encompass all levels of a power system, including generation, transmission, distribution, and end-consumers, by incorporating realistic operating conditions and field measurements. Additionally, new and emerging technologies such as synchrophasor measurement technologies, DERs, Energy Storage Systems (ESS), and grid-forming (GFM) inverters should be properly modelled to facilitate various investigations and future scenario analyses.
- **Integration of industrial equipment:** The environment must support the integration of industrial equipment commonly used in power systems. This includes industrial measuring units like phasor measurement units (PMUs) and smart meters, protection relays (e.g., overcurrent, differential, or distance protection), and flexible DERs (e.g., photovoltaic (PV) inverters, ESS). This integration ensures that realistic conditions and real-life equipment are incorporated into the testing environment, reflecting common industrial practices.
- **Interaction with Smart Grid Applications:** The sandboxing environment must be capable of interacting with various smart grid applications. This includes integrating monitoring, control, and protection applications to create in-the-loop interactions between the infrastructure and these applications. Integration should be achieved through standard communication protocols and data exchange through a real communication layer, which is crucial for investigating the impact of cyber-attacks on power system operations.
- **Isolated local communication network:** An isolated local communication network must be utilized to enable communication and data exchange within the sandboxing environment. Data exchange should be facilitated through standard communication protocols (e.g., IEEE C37.118, IEC 61850, Modbus - TCP, etc.) used in the power systems field. Incorporating an isolated network is essential to allow the development of actual cyber-attacks without affecting the organization's³ typical information and communication systems or being intercepted by the organization's firewall and security systems.
- **Execution of cyber-attack scenarios:** The sandboxing environment must support the easy execution of various cyber-attack scenarios and approaches. It should allow the development of actual cyber-attacks at the communication level of the isolated network, considering scenarios such as man-in-the-middle attacks, false data injection, and denial of service. Additionally, virtual cyber-attacks should be emulated across multiple internal communication channels to investigate the broader impact of cyber-attacks on power system infrastructure.
- **Data collection and analysis:** The sandboxing environment should enable data collection of both power measurements and communication traffic. Mechanisms must be in place to collect key electrical measurements (e.g., voltage, current, active power, reactive power)

³ With organization here we refer to the organization hosting the sandboxing infrastructure.

with adequate resolution and accuracy. Whenever possible, both actual and attacked measurements/set-points should be collected to facilitate improved analysis. In the case of actual attacks on the communication network, communication packages and traffic must also be captured.

- **Third-party application integration:** The sandboxing environment should support over-the-internet and in-the-loop interactions with third-party applications (e.g., cyber services for EPES). While typical smart grid applications will be integrated through the local isolated network, it is also important to allow integration with additional third-party applications over-the-internet communication. This integration should enable bidirectional data exchange in real-time, facilitated through standard and secure communication interfaces ensuring fast and straightforward integration without requiring the migration and installation of these applications on servers within the sandboxing facilities or the establishment of secure virtual private network (VPN) channels.

1.2.2 Sandboxing architecture

The overall architecture of the KIOS CoE sandboxing environment for cyber-physical analysis of EPES is illustrated in Figure 1. The sandboxing architecture is carefully designed to fulfil the key requirements outlined in the previous section.

Figure 1 KIOS CoE Sandboxing architecture (developed within the laboratory facilities of the power systems' group).

The architecture of the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing environment relies on the following key components and layers:

- **Power System Real-Time Digital Twin:** The digital twin serves as the cornerstone of the sandboxing architecture, utilizing a simulation engine to provide accurate and high-fidelity emulation of modern power system operations in real-time. This creates a realistic and non-invasive virtual environment for conducting cyber-security investigations. Detailed information about the digital twin developed for the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing is provided in Section 1.3.
- **Power-HIL:** A notable feature of the sandboxing environment is its capability to enable Power Hardware-in-the-Loop (Power-HIL) setups. This allows real-time interaction between actual power equipment (e.g., PMUs, smart meters, protection relays, inverters, ESS) and the digital twin under various cyber-attacks or different conditions emulated within the digital twin. This is facilitated through a bidirectional power amplifier that converts operating conditions calculated by the digital twin into real-life voltage and current conditions. More details about the Power-HIL layer are presented below.
- **Control-HIL:** Another important characteristic of the sandboxing environment is its capability to facilitate interactions between various smart grid control applications and the

power system digital twin in a Control-HIL configuration. A wide range of smart grid applications can be incorporated, including wide area monitoring, control and protection solutions, substation protection schemes, energy management and control of DERs, active distribution grid and microgrid controllers. Through Control-HIL setups, data is periodically exchanged between the digital twin and the smart grid applications via industrial communication protocols, allowing for the performance of cyber-attacks and the investigation of their impact on power infrastructure. Further details for Control-HIL are available in Section 1.5.

- **Communication Layer:** A local communication network is integrated into the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing architecture to enable data exchange between the digital twin (and field power equipment) and smart grid control applications. Cyber-attacks can be conducted on this local communication network, necessitating its isolation from the organization's main communication network during attacks to prevent interception by the organization's security systems. More details about the communication layer are provided in Section 1.6.
- **Cyber-Attacks Tools:** Given that the KIOS cyber-physical sandbox is developed for investigating cyber-attacks in power systems within a non-invasive environment, incorporating cyber-attack tools into the architecture is essential. The proposed sandbox supports two approaches for conducting attacks: (a) actual cyber-attacks launched within the isolated local area network by sniffing, analysing, altering, and injecting communication packets, and (b) virtual cyber-attacks performed in various data-exchange channels within the digital twin environment by adjusting measurements/set-points exchanged during operation. Both approaches are valuable for demonstrating and evaluating the effectiveness of cyber-security detection and prevention solutions, as well as investigating the broader impact of cyber-attacks. Further details about these tools are presented in Section 1.7.
- **Integration of Third-Party Applications:** A data-exchange interface and tailored middleware have been developed and integrated into the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing environment to enable standardized, secure, over-the-internet interaction between the sandbox and third-party applications, including selected components and tools developed as part of other research projects. Bidirectional interaction is facilitated through Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) that use distinct credential-based authorization for reading (measurements) or writing (set-points) from or to the power system digital twin. More details about the integration of third-party applications are provided in Section 1.8.

Overall, the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing architecture is designed to meet all functional requirements while providing a flexible environment where simple and complex cyber-attacks can be performed on various power domain applications. This sandbox can be used to validate and demonstrate various cyber-security solutions to detect, prevent, and mitigate cyber-attacks, as well as to assess the impact of certain cyber-attacks on power system infrastructure. The development of the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing environment is detailed in the following subsections and its use in various Sandboxing Use Cases (SUC) is presented in several other linked documents.

1.3 Power system digital twin

The power system digital twin serves as the cornerstone of the sandboxing architecture, leveraging a dedicated simulation engine to deliver accurate, high-fidelity emulation of modern power system operations in real-time. Through the digital twinning, a realistic and non-invasive virtual environment is established for conducting comprehensive cyber-security investigations on modern power systems.

1.3.1 Digital twin developing process

For the development of the digital twin, data from actual or typical test systems and real-life field measurements are required to construct detailed and dynamic simulation models that authentically replicate power system operating conditions. Additionally, new and emerging technologies are modelled and integrated within the digital twin to create various future scenarios. The final model is then properly converted and built for execution on a dedicated Real-time Simulator, ensuring adherence to real-time execution constraints. Furthermore, analog and digital communication interfaces are configured to facilitate interaction between the digital twin and external equipment or controllers.

The following steps have been undertaken to develop the digital twin environment:

- **Step 1 - Power Grid Topology and Data:** The initial step involves selecting the power system under test and collecting all relevant information about its topology and the modelling data for each system component.
- **Step 2 - Power System Simulation Model:** Once the topology and modelling information are available, the simulation model is designed. The simulation software and model characteristics are determined based on the associated Real-Time Simulator (RTS) to ensure real-time execution. For this sandboxing environment, an OPAL-RT 5707 real-time simulator, compatible with MATLAB/Simulink, is used. The power system is modelled using Simscape Electrical⁴ and Specialized Power Systems⁵ libraries from Mathworks to develop an electromagnetic (EMT) simulation model. A discrete-time fixed-step MATLAB solver is used with a microsecond-scale step (e.g., 50 μ s, 100 μ s) to achieve high accuracy and fidelity. After developing the model, various debugging and testing processes are performed to ensure stability and proper operation under different grid conditions.
- **Step 3 - Enhancing the Power System with New and Emerging Technologies:** Once a stable power system model is available, additional technologies can be integrated to accurately represent modern or future conditions. Such technologies may include inverter-based DERs for renewable energy and storage systems, electric vehicle charging points, and phasor measurement units (PMUs) with Global Positioning System (GPS)-synchronized measurements for wide area monitoring and control. These technologies typically come with specific communication interfaces that must be incorporated into the modelling process to facilitate the digital transition of the power system under test. The integration of these technologies requires further debugging and testing.
- **Step 4 - Real-Time Execution of the Digital Twin Model:** A key feature of the digital twin is its capability for real-time execution. Accurate EMT simulations for power grids involve high computational complexity and require a microsecond-scale solver step to capture the

⁴ <https://www.mathworks.com/products/simscape-electrical.html>

⁵ <https://www.mathworks.com/help/sps/specialized-power-systems.html>

dynamic performance of power systems. To achieve this, a dedicated RTS, such as the OPAL-RT 5707, is used to accelerate execution time and meet real-time constraints. The developed simulation model (from steps 1-3) must be modified for the specific RTS using eMEGASIM⁶ software, ARTEMIS⁷ electrical toolbox, and RT-LAB⁸ simulation control platform from OPAL-RT. These modifications include decoupling the power system into smaller subsystems, replacing MATLAB library components with ARTEMIS components, and splitting the system into multiple cores for real-time execution. The modified model is then compiled and built through the RT-LAB platform and loaded into the RTS for real-time execution.

- **Step 5 - Integration of real-life field measurements:** To enable the digital twin to replicate actual power grid operations or synthesize realistic operating conditions, field measurements are utilized. These measurements, typically load consumption or power generation time-series data, are used as input to the real-time simulation model to replicate real-life conditions. Data can be fed either during the initialization process to pre-load the profile for the investigation period (e.g., 1 hour, 1 day) or in real-time by receiving live field measurements through a communication interface.
- **Step 6 – Configure the required communication interfaces:** A crucial aspect of the digital twin is its capability to interact with power equipment (Power-HIL) or digital controllers (Control-HIL). For Power-HIL setups, the interaction between the digital twin and power devices (e.g., PMUs, inverters) is facilitated through an analogue output interface that drives a power amplifier connected with the device under test to convert the digital twin's operating conditions in real-life voltage and current. To close the loop in such Power-HIL setups, analogue measurements regarding the operation of the device under test are provided as input to the digital twin through an analogue input channel to be considered in the next solver step of the digital twin. For Control-HIL setups, interaction between the digital twin and control applications running on individual controllers is facilitated through periodic data exchange via digital communication protocols (e.g., Transmission Communication Protocol/Internet Protocol (TCP/IP), IEC 61850, IEEE C37.118, Modbus TCP). Thus, all necessary communication interfaces for the final digital twin model running on the RTS must be configured according to the needs of each use case.

These steps ensure the development of a robust and flexible digital twin environment capable of supporting comprehensive cyber-security investigations and integrating future technology advancements in modern power systems.

1.3.2 A common test system as a digital twin for various smart grid use cases

A comprehensive test power system has been designed and developed as a digital twin, within the OPAL-RT 5707 real-time simulator. This model includes conventional generation units, a transmission grid, a distribution grid, and a microgrid, with emerging technologies integrated to accurately represent a modern power system. Field measurements have been incorporated to

⁶ <https://www.opal-rt.com/system-emegasim/>

⁷ <https://www.opal-rt.com/solver/>

⁸ <https://www.opal-rt.com/software-rt-lab/>

synthesize realistic operating conditions. The common digital twin developed for the KIOS cyber-physical sandboxing environment is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Diagram of a EPES test system as a digital-twin.

This common and holistic model is designed to leverage the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox for investigating a wide range of smart grid use cases. It can be utilized for applications such as wide area monitoring and control, energy management for DERs, various power system protection schemes, active distribution grid management, and microgrid control solutions.

The key characteristics of the common digital twin model are described below:

- **Transmission grid and conventional generation units:** The transmission and generation levels of the sandboxing digital twin model are based on the topology and characteristics of the IEEE 9-bus test system, enhanced with three conventional synchronous generation units to partially cover the demand, as shown in Figure 2. Each generation unit is equipped with an associated turbine and governor controller, as well as an excitation and automatic voltage regulation system, to accurately capture the dynamic behaviour of the power system. All modelling data for the transmission and generation components of the digital twin are openly available⁹.
- **Active distribution grid and micro-grid:** At a selected bus of the transmission grid (i.e., bus 6), a medium voltage (MV) distribution grid is connected, consisting of 15 distribution substations/buses, as shown in Figure 2. The distribution grid typically operates in a radial configuration under normal conditions; however, breakers are available to enable a transition from radial to mesh re-configuration if needed. The distribution line parameters are based on typical distribution line parameters used in Cyprus distribution grid. PV generation and load demand are modelled in an aggregated manner at each MV substation using synthesized data derived from real-life field measurements. Additionally, each MV feeder is equipped with an ESS featuring GFM inverter capabilities, allowing operation in both grid-connected and autonomous modes. Consequently, the active distribution grid can also function as a microgrid, supporting islanding operation either as a whole or per MV feeder.

⁹ <https://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy/testsystems/index.php/ieee-9-bus-modified-test-system/>

- Measuring and protection devices:** In the common digital twin model of the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox, various measuring and protective devices have been integrated. At the transmission level, each bus is equipped with both conventional asynchronous measurements (e.g., voltage- V , active power- P , reactive power- Q) taken every few seconds, and synchronized PMU measurements (measuring both voltage and current phasors in a GPS-synchronized manner) every 20 ms. The PMU measurements are aggregated into a phasor data concentrator using the IEEE C37.118 communication protocol. In selected transmission substations and lines, various protection relays have been incorporated to ensure grid protection during short-circuit events. The operation and coordination of these protective devices are facilitated through data exchange via IEC 61850/Sampled Values and GOOSE protocols. Similarly, for monitoring the operation of the distribution grid, conventional asynchronous measurements (e.g., V , P , Q) taken every few seconds are integrated at each MV substation. These measurements support the active management of the distribution grid and microgrid. Relays and breaking devices are also integrated into the distribution grid to enable grid re-configuration actions, and breakers facilitate the islanding and re-synchronization transitions of the microgrid.
- Renewable Energy Sources and flexible DERs:** To replicate the operation of a modern power system, renewable energy sources (RES) and flexible DERs are integrated into the common digital twin model. In the transmission grid, a wind farm is integrated at bus 5, with a generation profile derived from a real-life 10.8 MW wind farm¹⁰ located in Larnaca, Cyprus, recorded at 30-second intervals. Additionally, a flexible DER consisting of a 40 MWh ESS and a 40 MVA grid-following inverter is integrated at bus 8, as shown in Figure 2. Active (P) and reactive (Q) power measurements are available every few seconds from both the wind farm and the flexible DER, and the operation of the ESS-based DER can be externally regulated according to active and reactive power set-points. In the distribution grid, an aggregated PV plant is modeled at each MV substation, with generation profiles synthesized by scaling measurements from real-life PV plants¹¹ located in Nicosia, adjusted according to the installed capacity at each substation. Additionally, flexible ESS-based DERs are installed at each MV feeder, each equipped with a 500 kVA inverter operating in GFM mode to support the islanded operation of microgrids. These DER inverters can be regulated by either internal or external set-points. Notably, RES measurements and external set-points for DERs in both the transmission and distribution grids are communicated through Modbus TCP protocols.

The common digital twin model presented in in Figure 2 and described above holistically represents the operation of a modern power system. This digital twin is executed in the OPAL-RT real-time simulator and is utilized for investigating various SUCs, which will be further discussed in the related documents.

1.4 Power – HIL

A key feature of the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox architecture relies on its capability to support Power-Hardware-in-the-Loop (Power-HIL) testbed configurations. This allows for the investigation of how actual power equipment (e.g., PMUs, smart meters, protection relays, inverters, ESS, etc.)

¹⁰ <https://aeolian-dynamics.com.cy/data-room/#livedata>

¹¹ <http://wisewiresolutions.com/live-demo/>

interacts with the digital twin under various cyber-attacks or different conditions emulated within the digital twin.

The Power-HIL requires the in the loop interaction between the digital twin, the power amplifier, and the field equipment (device under test), as illustrated in Figure 3. The Power-HIL capabilities are enabled when the following three conditions are met by the sandboxing architecture, as described below:

- **Real-time digital twin execution:** The digital twin must be capable of executing with a microsecond-scale solver step while adhering to hard real-time constraints. This ensures high-fidelity, accurate, and timely simulation of dynamic power system operations, while allowing the physical interaction with an actual device in real-time.
- **Available power amplification:** A power amplifier converts the operating conditions calculated within the digital twin into real-life voltage and current conditions. This is achieved through fast analogue communication interfaces, allowing the real-life power equipment to be driven accurately according to the simulated scenarios. In certain cases, bidirectional capabilities may be required for the power amplifier, while certain technical restriction regarding the nominal voltage, current and power of the power amplifier must be carefully considered for each Power-HIL testing setup.
- **Feedback signals integration:** Operating measurements from the field equipment must be provided as feedback to the digital twin for execution in each solver step. This creates a closed-loop system where real-time data from the physical equipment influences the simulation and vice versa, enabling precise interaction and analysis. The feedback signal is required in micro-seconds level and thus, analogue input channels are required in the digital twin.

Figure 3: Power-HIL configuration approach with In-the-Loop interaction between the digital twin, the power amplifier, and the field equipment.

In the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment, two main power amplifiers are available to integrate various power equipment into a Power-HIL configuration, allowing for the comprehensive investigation of different use cases. The key technical characteristics of the amplifiers are listed below.

- **Power amplifiers technical characteristics:** A Puissance+ PCU-3X7000¹² bidirectional linear power amplifier is available for Power-HIL setups for the interaction of power devices (e.g., inverter, ESS, etc.) with power exchange up to 21 kVA and an OMICRON CMS 356¹³ switching amplifier for Power-HIL testing of measuring and protective relay equipment. In general, these power amplifiers receive low voltage analogue signals (e.g., $\pm 10V$) from the real-time simulator (digital twin) regarding the voltage and/or current operation of a selected node/line of the power system digital twin. Then, it precisely amplifies the voltage and/or current into an actual system scale (e.g., 0-400V, 0-32A, etc.) with a transient response of 10 μs to allow the interconnection of actual power devices. The amplifier can exchange bidirectional active and reactive power in four quadrants to drive the operation of power devices by replicating conditions emulated within the real-time simulator. The amplifier is also equipped with measuring sensor to provide direct analogue feedback to the real-time simulator (digital twin) to close the loop.

The KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment is also equipped with various power devices available in the University of Cyprus (UCY) power systems laboratory facilities that can be used as device under test in various Power-HIL setups according to the sandboxing use-cases' needs. Examples of the available equipment for Power-HIL testing is provided bellow:

- **Photovoltaic inverter:** Fronius Symo 5.0-3-M¹⁴ three-phase 5kVA inverter driven through a direct current (DC) emulator with PV emulation capabilities and supporting Modbus TCP communication.
- **Battery storage system:** Soltaro storage system with 3 single-phase 5kVA hybrid inverters (Hyper-5000)¹⁵ connected in a common DC bus with a total battery capacity of 15 kWh based on Lithium-Iron Phosphate (LiFePO₄) technology, supporting TCP/IP and Modbus RTU communication.
- **Smart meters:** Janitza UMG604¹⁶ electricity meter with power quality analyzer capabilities and SOCOMEC DIRIS A40¹⁷ smart meter, with Modbus TCP communication interface.
- **Pharos Measurement Units (PMUs):** Arbiter 1133A Power Sentinel¹⁸ and SEL 421/521¹⁹ PMUs communicate with a Phasor Data Concentrator (SEL-5073 SYNCHROWAVE²⁰), through IEEE C37.118 protocol.
- **Intelligent Electronic Devices (IEDs) and protection relays:** SEL 451²¹ overcurrent protection relay with analogue inputs, SEL 451 overcurrent protection relay with inputs based on Sampled Values according to IEC 61850 protocol, and SEL 421 distance protection relay. The coordination between these relays is enabled by data exchanged through IEC 61850/GOOSE-Manufacturing Message Specification (MMS) protocols.

¹² <https://www.puissanceplus.com/assets/produitspdf/ps-3x3000-ac-180v-26a.pdf>

¹³ <https://www.omicronenergy.com/download/document/DF442FC8-27EA-4D54-B3AB-C3C80191E072/>

¹⁴ <https://www.fronius.com/en-gb/uk/solar-energy/installers-partners/technical-data/all-products/inverters/fronius-symo/fronius-symo-5-0-3-m>

¹⁵ <https://soltaro.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/03/Manual-Soltaro-HYPER-LV-1P-AU1.08-AUS.pdf>

¹⁶ <https://www.janitza.com/products/umg-604-pro.html>

¹⁷ <https://apac.socomec.com/en/p/diris-a-40>

¹⁸ <https://www.arbiter.com/catalog/product/model-1133a-power-sentinel.php>

¹⁹ <https://selinc.com/products/421/>

²⁰ <https://selinc.com/products/5073/>

²¹ <https://selinc.com/products/451/>

Hence, by connecting in the loop the digital twin running in the OPAL-RT 5707 real-time simulator with the above power devices through the power amplifier, various Power-HIL setups can be configured to: examine the behaviour of physical devices according to realistic conditions emulated within the digital twin, demonstrate the effectiveness of different cyber-security solution in realistic conditions, and support the impact assessment of various attacks on power domain, providing invaluable insights into system vulnerabilities and resilience.

1.5 Control – HIL

Another crucial feature of the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment is its capability to facilitate interactions between various smart grid control applications and the power system digital twin through Control-HIL configurations. This functionality enables comprehensive testing and analysis of control strategies, enhancing the resilience of smart grid systems against cyber-attacks.

Figure 4: Control-HIL configuration approach with in the loop interaction between the digital twin and a smart grid controller.

To establish a Control-HIL setup, the digital twin running in the real-time simulator must ensure real-time execution, maintaining high fidelity and accuracy in simulating power system dynamics. The control application should be executed on a separate hardware platform, such as a digital controller, personal computer (PC), or server. These two systems must continuously exchange measurements and coordination signals via standard industrial communication protocols, as presented in Figure 4. This bidirectional data exchange allows the digital twin to interact seamlessly with the control hardware, enabling a realistic and effective environment for testing and analysis smart grid control applications and their resilience to cyber-attacks.

Overall, the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing architecture is carefully designed to support Control-HIL setups, as shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2. Various Control-HIL setups have been developed to enhance the functionalities of the sandboxing environment and support a wide range of smart grid use cases. These setups include:

- **Control-HIL for DER Energy Management and Control Applications:** This setup focuses on energy management and control applications for DERs, which are crucial for regulating their operation to achieve objectives such as tracking energy market operations, avoiding power imbalances, reducing electricity costs, or increasing profitability. In this context, a Control-HIL setup is developed where RESs and flexible DERs are emulated within the real-

time digital twin, and a DER controller operates on an individual PC/Server. The controller receives measurements from the digital twin, processes them, and determines coordination set-points to regulate the operation of flexible DERs. Measurements and set-points are exchanged via Modbus TCP. This setup can be enhanced with Power-HIL capabilities, where measurements are taken from a smart meter driven by the digital twin and control set-points are sent to an inverter connected in the loop via an amplifier. Cyber-attacks on Modbus TCP communication channels, using Man-In-The-Middle (MITM) and False Data Injection (FDI) techniques, can compromise the coordinated operation of DERs, impacting the overall power system operation, as it is further demonstrated in sandboxing use cases.

- **Control-HIL for Wide Area Synchrophasor-Based Applications:** These applications rely on PMU measurements to monitor, control, and protect power systems. In this setup, PMUs are either emulated within the digital twin or physically connected through Power-HIL. PMUs send GPS-synchronized measurements every 20 ms via IEEE C37.118 to a phasor data concentrator (PDC), installed in a server, which time-aligns, stores, and manages the data. Various wide-area monitoring and control applications retrieve measurements from the PDC to enhance situational awareness or process the data to ensure power system stability. For some time-critical protection applications, PMU measurements are directly received by an intelligent electronic device emulated within a Typhoon HIL402²² digital controller, which processes the measurements and provides trip signals to breakers simulated within the digital twin during short-circuits. This setup enables the investigation of scenarios where PMU communication via IEEE C37.118 is compromised by MITM and FDI cyber-attacks. A related use case is presented in a related document.
- **Control-HIL for Protection Applications in Power Substations:** This setup examines the operation of protection relays for substations. The digital twin running within the real-time simulator interacts in real-time with either an actual protection relay (e.g., SEL 451) or a digital controller (e.g., Typhoon HIL402). Two main configurations are examined: (a) differential protection relying on measurements received via IEC 61850/Sampled Values, and (b) coordinated overcurrent protection between upstream and downstream relays using IEC 61850/GOOSE. Cyber-attacks on these communication channels using MITM, FDI, and Message Suppression (MS) techniques can affect the protection operation. Demonstration of sandboxing use-cases in a Control-HIL setup for differential and coordinated overcurrent protection application are further presented in a related document and dataset.
- **Control-HIL for Active Distribution Grid and Microgrid Control Applications:** As DER penetration increases in the distribution grid, active management and microgrid functionalities are required. This setup involves a microgrid controller that receives measurements from each substation within the distribution grid/microgrid. The controller processes these measurements to manage islanding and resynchronization, while secondary controller regulates the power exchange and maintain stability. Data exchange between the digital twin and the microgrid controller occurs via standard communication protocols. Cyber-attacks on these channels using MITM and FDI techniques can severely impact the system's performance, as discussed in related document and dataset.

²² <https://www.typhoon-hil.com/doc/products/Typhoon-HIL402-brochure.pdf>

In summary, the Control-HIL setups developed within the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox support a wide range of smart grid applications under various cyber-attack scenarios. These setups can be modified to include Power-HIL capabilities or to address different applications as well. Data exchange between the digital twin and controllers uses standard power industry communication protocols (e.g., Modbus TCP, IEEE C37.118, IEC 61850), creating realistic conditions for testing and demonstrating cyber-security solutions for power systems.

1.6 Communication layer

A robust local communication network is a critical component of the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing architecture, facilitating seamless data exchange between the digital twin, field power equipment, and smart grid control applications. Under normal operation, this communication is managed through the University of Cyprus (UCY) local network, ensuring efficient interaction and coordination between the digital twin, power devices, and smart grid applications, as shown in Figure 5 (a).

Figure 5: Dual network setup used in KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing architecture: (a) Local area network used during normal (attack-free) operation of the sandboxing environment, (b) dual network configuration transferring the communication channels targeted by the attacker into an isolated local network.

To enable comprehensive cyber-security investigations, a distinct network configuration is employed when performing cyber-attacks. During the attack implementation, the relevant communication channels are transferred to an isolated local network, as presented in Figure 5 (b). This isolation is essential to prevent any potential interception or disruption by the UCY's primary

security systems, thereby protecting the integrity and security of the organization's main communication infrastructure. This dual-network setup allows for the execution of realistic cyber-attack scenarios within the sandbox environment. Researchers can assess vulnerabilities, test the resilience of smart grid applications, and develop robust countermeasures against cyber threats without risking the security of UCY's operational systems. By maintaining a clear separation between the normal operation network and the isolated network used during cyber-attacks, the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox provides a safe and effective platform for advancing cyber-security research and enhancing the reliability and security of modern power systems.

1.7 Cyberattack tools for the Sandboxing

The developed sandboxing environment facilitates the straightforward execution of various cyber-attack scenarios and methodologies. The sandbox supports the development of actual cyber-attacks at the communication level of the isolated network, encompassing scenarios such as MITM attacks, FDI, and Denial of Service (DoS). Additionally, the sandbox enables the emulation of virtual cyber-attacks within the digital twin environment across multiple internal communication channels to assess the broader impact of these attacks on power system infrastructure. The implementation details for actual and virtual attacks are thoroughly explained in the following subsections.

1.7.1 Actual attacks

The first approach to conducting cyber-attacks in the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox involves implementing actual attacks at the communication level of an isolated local network. The focus is on executing MITM, FDI, and DoS attack techniques on the communication channels of various smart grid applications to investigate their impact on power system operations.

Particular emphasis is given to client-server communication protocols widely used in smart grid applications, such as Modbus TCP, IEEE C37.118, and IEC 61850/GOOSE and SV. Implementing a MITM attack on these protocols involves an attacker secretly intercepting and potentially altering the communication between the power system (emulated by the digital twin) and the smart grid controller, as illustrated in Figure 6. The attacker makes both parties believe they are directly communicating with each other, while actually blocking or modifying the messages.

To initiate such an attack, all components (e.g., digital twin, power devices, smart grid controllers) must be connected to the local network through a network switch isolated from the UCY network. The attacker's PC, also connected to the switch, runs Ettercap – Kali-Linux²³ tool to perform the MITM attack. In the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment, the following process is used to conduct MITM, FDI, or DoS attacks:

- **Intercepting Communication:** The target devices (e.g., digital twin and controller) are selected using their IP addresses. By using Address Resolution Protocol (ARP) poisoning in Ettercap software, the attacker deceives the two targets into sending their traffic through the attacker's machine. ARP poisoning involves sending fake ARP messages to associate the attacker's Media Access Control (MAC) address with the IP addresses of the target devices.
- **Filtering Traffic:** Once in the middle, the attacker applies filters to selectively block or modify traffic. A DoS attack is performed by applying a filter to block traffic. For Modbus,

²³ <https://www.kali.org/tools/ettercap/>

the attacker blocks data on port 502 (the default port for Modbus TCP) while for IEEE C37.118, the attacker blocks data on the relevant TCP/ User Datagram Protocol (UDP) port used by this protocol. On the other hand, an FDI attack involves analysing the packets and using a filter to carefully alter the payload data within a communication packet. Different filters are created based on the type and objective of the cyber-attack.

- **Attack Impact:** After applying the attack filter, the communication channel between the two target IP addresses remains operational; however, any data packets related to the targeted protocol are either dropped (in the case of DoS) or altered (in the case of FDI).

(a) Communication flow after ARP spoofing

(b) Communication flow after packet filtering

Figure 6: Communication flow of packets during an actual MITM attack before and after FDI.

By following these steps, the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment can effectively conduct various cyber-attacks on smart grid operations allowing a playground to test cyber-security solution effectiveness and to assess the impact of a cyber-attack on power systems infrastructure.

1.7.2 Virtual attacks

The implementation of actual attacks in the communication network is a time-consuming process, requiring significant effort each time a new attack needs to be developed. Moreover, the targeted communication channels for cyber-attacks may be limited within the sandboxing environment. For example, in a Power-HIL configuration where only one PMU is physically connected in the loop while the rest are emulated within the digital twin, the attack surface is restricted to that single PMU, making it challenging to investigate simultaneous attacks on multiple PMUs and quantifying the larger impact on the power system.

To address this limitation and expand the sandboxing environment's capabilities, a virtual attack module has been developed, as illustrated in Figure 7. This module enables the straightforward development and execution of various attack strategies directly within the digital twin environment. The virtual attack module allows for the implementation of MITM and FDI attacks across multiple communication channels of client-server protocols, facilitating the alteration of measurements or set-point signals by the attacker.

Figure 7: Virtual attack module developed within the digital twin environment to straight-forward emulate a wide range of MITM and FDI attack targeting client-server protocols.

Through the virtual attack module, attacks can be emulated where the payload of communication packets is modified using four main approaches:

- **Multiplicative Alteration:** Adjusting the value by a multiplicative factor.
- **Offset Deviation:** Adding a fixed offset to the original value.
- **Value Replacement:** Replacing the original value with a specific one stacking the measurement or the set-point at a specific value.
- **Replay Attack:** Replaying previously captured data packets to mimic legitimate communication.

This virtual attack capability significantly enhances the sandboxing environment by allowing for the emulation of complex attack scenarios on multiple devices simultaneously, providing a more comprehensive framework for cyber-security investigations and testing in power systems domain.

1.8 Integration of 3rd party applications

The sandboxing environment is designed to support seamless over-the-internet and in-the-loop interactions with third-party applications. While typical smart grid applications (as discussed in Section 1.5) are integrated through the local isolated network, it is also essential to enable integration with additional third-party applications via over-the-internet communication. This integration allows for real-time, bidirectional data exchange through standard and secure communication interfaces (e.g., encrypted APIs), ensuring fast and straightforward integration without needing to migrate and install these third-party applications on servers within the sandboxing facilities or establish secure VPN channels. However, this integration is limited to applications where the data-exchange rate is on a seconds-scale or slower, due to the need to properly consider communication delays.

Figure 8: Third-party applications integration with the sandboxing environment through a local middleware and a cloud platform to facilitate standardized and over-the-internet data exchange.

To achieve the integration of such third-party applications with the KIOS Cyber-physical sandboxing environment, the following developments and activities have been performed, as illustrated in Figure 8:

- **Middleware development:** A dedicated middleware has been developed to handle data exchange with the real-time simulator locally. This middleware acts as an intermediary, ensuring that real-time data from the digital twin and physical devices of the sandboxing architecture is efficiently managed within the local network (firewall protected), without exposing devices to the internet, while considering either encrypted or unencrypted communication. The middleware runs on local hardware (i.e., server PC), with several modifications implemented within the digital twin model (running in the real-time simulator) to manage data exchange effectively.
- **Establishment of secure communication:** The middleware interacts with the cloud-based data management platform via an API-based standardized, encrypted (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure - HTTPS) over-the-internet communication, using a predefined and periodic data-exchange framework determined according to the sandboxing needs. This setup ensures compatibility and facilitates the secure and smooth flow of data between the sandboxing environment and external applications.
- **Cloud-based data management platform:** A cloud-based Internet of Things (IoT) data management platform, based on ThingSpeak, has been implemented to enable the integration of potential third-party applications by establishing a standardized and bidirectional data-exchange framework between the cloud platform and the sandboxing

environment via the intermediate middleware. This platform supports real-time data acquisition, processing, and analytics, allowing third-party applications to interact with the sandboxing environment without being physically co-located.

- **Integration with third-party applications:** Third-party applications are integrated through APIs with distinct credential-based authorization for reading (measurements) or writing (set-points) from or to the power system digital twin according to each application's requirements. The cloud-based platform provides a scalable and flexible solution for integrating a wide range of applications, enhancing the overall functionality and reach of the sandboxing environment.
- **User interface integration for remote management:** Through the middleware and the cloud-based platform, the sandboxing operation can be monitored and managed through dedicated user interfaces (as demonstrated in Figure 8), utilizing the same read/write APIs used for third-party applications. These user interfaces have been developed within the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox project using Grafana²⁴ and MATLAB App designer²⁵ software.
- **Dataset extraction:** The cloud-based platform can also be used to extract datasets regarding the sandboxing operation. This is achieved by utilizing the same read API-based requests to download data either as comma-separated value (CSV) or JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) files for a selected period according to the recorded measurements.

The combination of a robust middleware and a cloud-based Internet of Things (IoT) data management platform ensures that the sandboxing environment can accommodate diverse third-party applications, promoting innovation and collaboration in smart grid and cyber-security research and innovation context. This integration capability is critical for advancing the development and testing of new solutions and for validating the performance and security of existing systems in a realistic and controlled setting.

1.9 Sandboxing environment utilization

This advanced environment relies on a real-time power system digital twin, combined with various Control-HIL and Power-HIL setups. This combination enables a controlled and non-invasive platform for testing cyber-security solutions for modern power grids and investigating the impact of different cyber-attacks on power system operations.

For testing the effectiveness of various cyber-security solutions for power systems, the sandboxing environment has already been integrated with several third-party applications related to the above-mentioned projects. The sandboxing environment allows the demonstration of invasive attacks and security actions in a controlled environment without risking the integrity of the actual infrastructure.

Furthermore, five additional SUCs have been implemented to demonstrate the functional capabilities of the KIOS Cyber-physical sandbox. They showcase various cyber-attack scenarios in different smart grid applications and assess the impact of these cyber-attacks on each SUC scenario. The five SUCs are listed below and are presented in the linked documents related to this architecture and datasets.

²⁴ <https://grafana.com/>

²⁵ <https://www.mathworks.com/products/matlab/app-designer.html>

- SUC1: DER Energy Management and Control
- SUC2: Wide Area Protection
- SUC3: Differential Protection
- SUC4: Coordinated Overcurrent Protection
- SUC5: Management of Active Distribution Grid and Microgrid

For each SUC, various datasets based on electrical measurements and communication traffic have been collected, considering different cyber-attack scenarios in a wide range of applications in modern power systems. These datasets are made openly available to the wider community to boost activities and development in cyber-security solutions for smart grids.